

D2.4

User requirements and DAFNE+ architecture (final report)

Revision v1.0

Work package	WP2
Task	T2.4
Due date	31-12-2024
Submission date	27-12-2024
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Deliverable lead	NETCOMPANY INTRASOFT INTERNATIONAL S.A.
Version	V1.0
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Abstract

This deliverable presents a) the revised list of user requirements (based on the feedback and discussion that have taken place up to November 2024) b) the accordingly revised list of system requirements and c) the final DAFNE+ architecture that meets these revised requirements. The evolutions of the specifications were fed by feedback gathered from target users as they tested/used the platform (up to version 2), and by progress on the various dimensions of the project – technical (updated tools), legal, monetisation, DAO/governance and evaluation. These specifications define the framework and strategy for the commercial exploitation of the DAFNE+ outcomes.

Keywords

Use case, user feedback, blockchain, NFT, DAO, art, culture, heritage, sound, music, maker, design, open source

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
V0.1	19.11.2024	Document template with table of contents	Nelly Leligou (INTRA)
V0.2	29.11.2024	User requirements on Part 3	Hugues Vinet (IRCAM)
V0.3	09.12.2024	System requirements on Part 4	Dimitrios Skias (INTRA)
V0.4	11.12.2024	System architecture on Part 5	Frederico Bosco (ENG)
V0.5	13.12.2024	Updates on Part 4 and Part 5	Dimitrios Skias (INTRA), Filisia Melissari (SYN)
V0.6	16.12.2024	Peer-review ready version	Dimitrios Skias (INTRA)
V0.7	20.12.2024	Peer-review feedback	Iago Fernández-Cedrón (UPM), Toby Dubois-Heys (MMU)
V0.8	23.12.2024	Peer-review consolidation	Dimitrios Skias (INTRA)
V1.0	27.12.2024	Final submission version	Iago Fernández-Cedrón (UPM)

Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC	Creative Commons
DAO	Decentralised Autonomous Organisation
DoA	Description of Action
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FL	Federated Learning
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IPFS	Inter Planetary File System
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LFS	Large File Storage
MoSCoW	Must, Should, Could, Will not have
ND	Non-Derivative
NN	Neural Network
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
SA	Share-alike
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the evolution of the user requirements that were presented in D2.1 [1] as they have been revised capitalizing on the users' feedback gained through testing and using the DAFNE+ platform (version 2) and constructive discussions that have crystalized the progress made in various dimensions covering technical, legal, DAO/governance, monetisation and evaluation aspects, in the context of the project execution until the moment of writing these lines. Then, the system requirements were revised to reflect the changes introduced. The list of user requirements follows a prioritised classification following the MoSCoW (Must, Should, Could, Will not have) approach that was adopted in the previous iteration of this document. Finally, this document describes the final version of the DAFNE+ architecture that complies with the refined requirements, and which will dictate the final development enhancements incorporated in the final DAFNE+ platform (version 3).

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and contents of the document

This deliverable presents

- the final (revised) version of the user requirements which has been produced based on the initial list of user requirements (presented in D2.1 [1]) with additions and modifications that occurred due to the feedback collected during the piloting activities and the evolution of all activities of the project (including legal and monetisation aspects).
- The final (revised) version of the DAFNE+ platform architecture which has been produced based on D2.2 [2] and the revised system requirements triggered by the revised user requirements. Additionally, slight modifications were dictated by the experience from the first development and integration cycle of the platform.

2.2 Document structure

The document structure follows the logical structure of the generation of a final architecture which is:

- Chapter 1: executive summary
- Chapter 2: Introduction
- Chapter 3: revised user requirements list
- Chapter 4: revised system requirement list
- Chapter 5: final DAFNE+ architecture.

In the end of this document, conclusions are drawn.

2.3 Dependencies to-from other WPs

This deliverable depends on:

- WP3 and WP4 for the feedback resulting from the existing state of tools and platform
- WP5 for the results of the piloting activities
- WP6 for the legal, governance and monetisation frameworks applicable to all use cases.

- WP7 for the discussions that have results in better understanding of the end users of the platform from DAFNE+ partners.
- It provides valuable information to:
 - WP3 and WP4 for the development of the last version of the different components
 - WP4 for use case requirements on the next platform version
 - WP7 for the definition of appropriate messages for dissemination and for the design of sound exploitation/business plans.

It is worth noting that **DAFNE+ consortium has decided to prioritise the user requirements**, prior to delivering this document to the technical WPs (i.e. WP3 and WP4) for the development of the final version of the platform as the remaining time may turn out to be insufficient for meeting all new/revised requirements.

3 Feedback Analysis

3.1 Introduction

This part presents an analysis of the user requirements on the DAFNE+ platform since its first release (V1) at the end of 2023. This first platform version resulted from the user feedback process carried out in the first part of the project and presented in deliverable D2.2 [2] – Use case specifications and their analysis and translation to functional specifications presented in deliverable D2.1 [1] - User requirements and DAFNE+ architecture.

This presentation is structured in two updates corresponding to two successive user feedback periods and platform versions:

- User feedback and requirements based on the version V1 and its incremental updates between January and June 2024: this feedback led to an updated specification of the use cases documented in deliverable D2.3 [3] – Use case specifications – final report, and an update of the related user requirements presented in Part 11 of D2.3.
- User feedback and requirements based on an intermediate platform update (V2) released early October 2024 and incorporating part of user requirements documented in D2.3. The purpose of these final user requirements is to focus on the major platform developments expected for the final major release (V3), scheduled for Q1 2025, and to feed the final use case pilot phase.

3.2 First update of user requirements – June 2024

The following table elaborates on the final version of the use case specification presented in D2.3 from which the following user requirements have been extracted and structured in the following table in a compact way. Column *New* concerns new specifications added to those already present in D2.1. It is worth noting that some features may have been already mentioned in their general principles from the first specifications in D2.1 but may have led to more detailed user requirements at later stages. Column *V2* concerns features implemented in successive platform updates from V1 and present in the V2 release.

User requirements – first update	New	V2
----------------------------------	-----	----

1. Platform features			
	1.1. Asset management and publication		
	1.1.1. Stability of the connection to the MetaMask plugin	✓	✓
	1.1.2. Full connection between the Content Manager and the NFT Marketplace	✓	✓
	1.1.3. Possibility to create NFTs directly from the Content Management	✓	✓
	1.1.4. Additional type of contents (e.g., work repositories)		✓
	1.1.5. Additional asset information and metadata, including work title, composer name and work version, for work repositories. Links to work author and work presentation.		✓
	1.1.6. Addition of a markdown parser for read.me files.	✓	
	1.1.7. Facilitation of the usage of the Content Management (tutorials and tooltips)	✓	✓
	1.1.8. Enhancement of the Organisation and Teams section (both in terms of UI and functionalities)	✓	✓
	1.1.9. Implementation of a reputation system, including metrics and badges bases on items	✓	
	1.1.10. Implementation of an asset versioning system	✓	
	1.1.11. Revision of the licensing models, including the possibility for a new user to request the right to produce a new version of a specific content, keeping at the same time the ownership rights to the original creator.	✓	

1.2. Community management and DAO			
1.2.1.	Introduction of the DAFNE+ Governance DAO managing a single community	✓	✓
1.2.2.	Process for submission, discussion and votes of DAO proposals	✓	✓
1.3. Monitoring and evaluation			
1.3.1.	Implementation of Matomo for tracking the users' behaviour in the platform in order to collect relevant metrics.	✓	✓
2. User experience			
2.1 User interfaces			
2.1.1.	Have more consistent interfaces of the various platform sections, and also with the DAFNE+ website	✓	✓
2.1.2.	Have a landing page highlighting the platform features and how to get started	✓	
2.1.3.	Emphasise the MetaMask logo and its purpose.	✓	✓
2.1.4.	Enhanced interfaces of the Organisation and Teams section	✓	✓
2.1.5.	Enhanced user workflow starting with the Organisation and Teams section and then uploading and publishing content	✓	✓
2.1.6.	Enhancements of the Marketplace design and layout, based on mock-ups and style designs	✓	✓
2.1.7.	Enhancement of the visualisation of digital assets in the marketplace	✓	✓

	2.1.8.	External access to some sections by users not registered in the platform: Marketplace, tutorials and FAQ.	☑	
	2.2.	Documentation and user support		
	2.2.1.	Production of documentation (including FAQs) and tutorials on the main user onboarding workflows: acquisition and connection to a MetaMask wallet, acquisition of free tokens, creation of contents, minting, buying and selling of NFTs	☑	☑
	2.2.2.	Extension of tutorials and short videos to user workflows beyond first steps	☑	☑
	2.2.3.	Explanations on general concepts of blockchains, NFTs, DAOs, the way they are used in the platform and the benefits that this technology can provide to the end-users.	☑	☑

TABLE 1: LIST OF USER REQUIREMENTS FOR THE FIRST UPDATE

3.3 Second update of user requirements – December 2024

This second requirements update is new, and its outcomes are described in more detail below. The use case representatives were asked to list the most important developments expected for the latest platform release and, for the most complex features, to specify them with user journeys and suggestions for user interfaces. The content below reflects the collaborative process followed and lists the discussion artifacts that subsequently were utilized to produce the final version of user and system requirements. Some of the requirements overlapped and defined in more detail requirements already expressed in previous processes but not yet implemented in the platform V2. The process culminated in a meeting with use case representatives and technical partners to agree on the level of priority for implementing each requirement, taking into account both its importance to the use cases and the constraints on implementation within existing resources by the end of the project. The MoSCoW (Must, Should, Could, Will not have) labelling system used for the initial specification process was retained for the prioritisation.

The Use Cases that concern DAFNE+ are listed below:

- Use case 1 - User generated content at large for heritage
- Use case 2 - Experimental sound/music production
- Use case 3 - Novel forms of artistic content exploitation

3.3.1 Platform features

3.3.1.1 Manage assets versioning

3.3.1.1.1 Short description and motivation:

Manage collections of assets as successive versions of an initial one with specific rules of shared ownership/revenue, and attribution involving the initial owners. Bring a support for collaborative work based on assets re-use.

3.3.1.1.2 UC1 User journey:

Versioning of the asset created by the owner/creator, who adds this permission to the asset to be reused by other creators. It would be good to have this option possible to add at later time not just at the time of the creation of the NFT. Does the asset need to be editable for this? Would it require modifications done within the DAFNE+ platform only to keep track of the versioning? Can the creator add the versioning at the later time? If only at the creation of the listing, then it should have further guidance about the process behind it.

3.3.1.1.3 UC2 User journey:

The choice between 3 licensing options, compatible with the CC and Token Bound licenses, shall be proposed to the initial asset owner and NFT creator: either ND (Non-derivative) or “ND by default with owner authorisation required” or SA (share alike). The selected option shall be listed in the detailed asset information in the Marketplace. The creator shall also enter a version number in the form x.y.z (x,y, and z integers) for the initial asset version (by default 1.0.0). If “ND by default with owner authorisation required” was chosen, the initial owner shall acknowledge to be contacted by relevant means, i.e. either email or discord contact (or better: private and anonymous messaging system managed in the platform).

- the SA option implies that anyone is authorised to produce and distribute a derived work including a new version of the asset. If it applies to the asset, any registered user may have access to a contextual menu (e.g. by right-clicking on the icon of any version of the asset) and be able to mint a new NFT

presented as a new version of the asset. The user shall enter a version number superior to all other versions of the same asset.

- if the ND option is selected (without owner authorisation required), no-one is authorised to produce a new version, and this possibility shall not be offered by the UI.
- if the ND, by default with owner authorisation required, is selected, when right-clicking on the icon of the NFT related to any version of the asset, a menu item will ask him/her to confirm his/her will to contact the initial owner for getting the authorisation of producing a new version. The platform will then provide the agreed communication channel between both. Once communication has been established and if the owner agrees to grant the new user a right to produce a new version, a protocol shall be defined. The easiest approach would be a menu item accessible to the initial owner by right-clicking on the NFT icon and a dialog asking to enter the new user ID and the version number (superior to all existing versions) that the new user will be allowed to produce.

In the Marketplace, the GUI should relate all versions of a same asset. If the choice is made to have one icon per version, they shall for instance have all the same name and visual identity and be differentiated by their version number.

3.3.1.1.4 UC3 User journey:

The choice between 3 licensing options, compatible with the CC and Token Bound licenses, shall be proposed to the initial asset owner and NFT creator: (1) ND, (2) ND by default with owner authorisation required or (3) SA (share alike). (1) and (2) options follow the same approach introduced in UC2 having the preferred option of private and/ or anonymous messaging system managed in the platform. (3) the SA option implies that anyone is authorised to (re)produce and distribute a derived work including a new version of the asset. The registered user can mint a new NFT through a new version of the asset. The new version automatically should have new version number applied. (e.g. V1.1 > minted > V1.2). When the user reuploads the asset and made significant changes to that asset. They can change the version number e.g. V1.2 minted, reupload as version V2.0 - with significant changes and/or add-ons. (Ideally this process is automated). The new updated assets must respect the original license. However, the new features of the assets may differ from the original license. For example, V1.1 has CC BY-NC-SA and V2.0 has CC BY-NC-SA and the new parts of this asset are licensed under CC BY-SA.

3.3.1.1.5 Simplified User journey:

This one is intended as a simplified, common ground for all of them:

- each asset should have a version, by default 1.0.0.
- the creator of a new asset can declare inheritance from several other assets with a percentage of ownership for each parent. It is up to the creator of the new asset to decide if it is a new version of one of its parents (with same name and increasing version number and thus being considered as an implementation of the same work) or if it has a new name and possible version renumbering from 0.0.1.
- forking: in the same way, either the new asset is a new version of an existing work and must have a version superior to all existing assets, or it diverges from it with a new name and relates to a new work with possible version renumbering from 0.0.1.
- the possibility of renumbering an asset version after its creation, which would have consequences on its children's assets is to be checked.
- if too complicated we can give up the "ND by default with owner authorisation required" option, so that the creation of a derived asset is possible only if for each parent either the ND option was not selected or if the creator of the derived asset is an owner of it.
- the possible licensing options are derived from a combination of the most restrictive options of the parents (see the standard table of combinations for CC options).

3.3.1.1.6 Priority for implementation:

This feature is a top priority for all 3 use cases, and the Should priority was agreed considering potential inconsistencies between use cases and uncertainties for implementation.

3.3.1.2 Manage multiple NFT instances for an asset

3.3.1.2.1 Short description and motivation:

Required for all use cases/scenarios relying on a principle of distribution and not ownership transfer. The number of instances may be predefined by the owner. An alternate possibility may be to propose an "unlimited distribution" mode with the automatic generation of a new NFT based on the same asset when the NFT is sold. In the Marketplace interface, all NFT instances pointing to the same asset shall be represented by a single icon.

3.3.1.2.2 UCI User journey:

The possibility to have Limited Editions, meaning a limited number of the same asset can be created. The versioning for this could be implemented linking to the owner and the creator. This option would have a restriction on the number that is applied which would not be possible to change later.

3.3.1.2.3 UC2 User journey:

When creating an NFT, either from the Marketplace or Content Manager, the number of NFT instances is asked to the user. If possible, the unique asset icon in the Marketplace GUI includes the number of available instances. Each NFT acquisition decreases the counter of available instances. The NFT information provides the list of users (wallet IDs) having bought the instance.

3.3.1.2.4 UC3 User journey:

Does not differ to UC2.

3.3.1.2.5 Priority for implementation:

This feature was labelled as a Must: the ability to give multiple users access to an asset via NFTs is common to all use cases and is not difficult to implement.

3.3.1.3 Implementation of a derived version of the Token Bound license for NFTs

3.3.1.3.1 Short description and motivation:

Bring a more robust legal framework for NFT based licenses. Adapt the Token Bound license conditions to specific use cases requirements.

3.3.1.3.2 Priority for implementation:

This feature is essential both in its legal relevance and in Use Cases 2 and 3, where assets including copyrighted material are managed. A derived version of the Token Bound License is required to prevent NFT owners from redistributing the assets elsewhere.

However, this feature request was not specified more in detail after the conclusion of an internal technical study: the use of ERC-721¹ as a replacement of ERC-1155² would require too deep modifications in the current platform mechanisms, in particular:

- It adds complexity to the approval and transfer mechanisms, particularly due to the batch nature of ERC-1155.

¹ <https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-721>

² <https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-1155>

- The contract would require more storage and potentially more gas for operations, which could impact usability and adoption.

The priority level was therefore labelled as Should.

3.3.1.4 User as a search result

3.3.1.4.1 Short description and motivation:

In the Marketplace, it would be useful to be able to obtain all results related to an author by typing his/her name in the search bar.

3.3.1.4.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Could.

3.3.2 Community management and DAO

3.3.2.1 DAO voting for competitions between asset proposals

3.3.2.1.1 Short description and motivation:

Extend the DAO mechanism of proposals submissions and votes to the management of community votes based on a selection between different proposals represented by published assets. The initial motivation is to bring a support to the RAVE models competition managed as part of use case 2.

3.3.2.1.2 UC2 User journey:

Allow participation in a vote published prior to account creation. Allow if possible, for non-NFT based votes (meaning a free but identified vote). We wish the voters not to be obliged to get a wallet as the applicants do not need a wallet to submit content to the contest. Add the possibility to hide or remove a contest from the list (especially for test contest to be hidden or removed):

- Add hyperlink (rich text) to the description of a DAO vote.
- Type: Add a competition type in the menu
- Additional field: Link to competition
 - Option 1, 2... linked to "view linked content" of a competition
 - Option 1, 2... allow for clickable URL
 - Option 1, 2... Don't restrict the text field to 50 characters, especially if you have a URL

Possibility of ordering options or multiple votes (option 3, option 25 and option 16 in order of preference, for example).

3.3.2.1.3 Priority for implementation:

The potential interest of this feature for the management and development of the DAFNE+ community as an extension of the development of the Governance DAO led to label it Must.

3.3.2.2 DAO discussion space - Discord link

3.3.2.2.1 Short description and motivation:

Based on the entry point in the Proposal creation phase, two options: 1) Do you already have the Discord Governance Thread link for your Proposal? 2) If not automatically create the Discord Governance channel with the Name of the New Proposal in a thread.

3.3.2.2.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Should.

3.3.2.3 DAFNE+ treasury flow

3.3.2.3.1 Short description and motivation:

Create fund allocation from common wallet towards content creators with approved proposals for new projects or at least a UI for the common wallet - Owners should see how much the platform gained from the transaction fee.

3.3.2.3.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Could.

3.3.2.4 Free item redistribution workflow

3.3.2.4.1 Short description and motivation:

Donate/support mechanism when a free license is used

3.3.2.4.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Could.

3.3.3 User experience

3.3.3.1 Platform landing page with value proposition

3.3.3.1.1 Short description and motivation:

A landing page that explains the benefits of the platform (What, Why & How), what one can do with it, potentially with a graphic overview of all features of the platform. Followed by the videos that are currently hosted on the landing page.

3.3.3.1.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Must.

3.3.3.2 Public access to the Marketplace

3.3.3.2.1 Short description and motivation:

The minted items should be available for visualisation without registration in order to attract and promote the platform.

3.3.3.2.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Must.

3.3.3.3 Link to Discord

3.3.3.3.1 Short description and motivation:

Direct and visible link to discord channel for people to connect (outside of the platform). Ensure to create a URL link that is valid forever.

3.3.3.3.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Must.

3.3.3.4 User in a drop-down menu to search for collaborators

3.3.3.4.1 Short description and motivation:

In the current implementation, a collaborator to be added to an organisation does not need to be already registered to the platform: an invitation email is sent. A drop-down select with the list of existing users should be added.

3.3.3.4.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Should.

3.3.3.5 Documentation on acquisition of new tokens

3.3.3.5.1 Short description and motivation:

Document (video tutorial, text) the process of Metamask configuration for the Polygon network regarding the update of the token name from MATIC to POL and the acquisition of free *testnet* tokens.

3.3.3.5.2 Priority for implementation:

The priority level was therefore labelled as Must.

3.3.4 Synthesis of user requirements – second update

The following table lists the user requirements of this second update using the same synthetic presentation as for the first update.

The *New* column concerns requirements not yet expressed in the first update. For requirements already expressed, the requirement number is the same one as for the first update. Otherwise, the requirement number is incremented. The column *Priority* adheres to the MoSCoW prioritisation level of the respective requirement.

User requirements – second update		New	Priority
1. Platform features			
1.1. Asset management and publication			
1.1.10.	Manage asset versioning	☑	Should
1.1.11.	Revision of the licensing models, including the possibility for a new user to request the right to produce a new version of a specific content, keeping at the same time the ownership rights to the original creator.	☑	Should
1.1.12.	Manage multiple NFT instances for an asset	☑	Must

	1.1.13. User as a search result	☑	Could
	1.1.14. Implementation of a derived version of the Token Bound license for NFTs	☑	Should
1.2. Community management and DAO			
	1.2.3. DAO voting for competitions between asset proposals	☑	Must
	1.2.4. DAO discussion space - Discord link	☑	Should
	1.2.5. DAFNE+ treasury flow	☑	Could
	1.2.6. Free item redistribution workflow	☑	Could
2. User experience			
2.1 User interfaces			
	2.1.2. Platform landing page with value proposition		Must
	2.1.8. Public access to Marketplace		Must
	2.1.9. Link to Discord	☑	Must
	2.1.10. User in a drop-down menu to search for collaborators	☑	Should
2.1. Documentation and user support			
	2.2.4. Documentation on acquisition of new tokens	☑	Must

TABLE 2: LIST OF USER REQUIREMENTS FOR THE SECOND UPDATE

4 System requirements

4.1 Introduction

This chapter produces a new iteration of system requirements based on the updated user requirements presented in the preceding chapters. (3.2, 3.3).

The new iteration of system requirements reflects ongoing updates based on user feedback, testing, and the integration of new features. As the platform evolves, it is important that the system requirements remain aligned with these developments to ensure the platform continues to meet user expectations and supports the overall project goals.

The process for compiling this updated version of system requirements is the following:

- The technical partners reviewed and processed the user requirements, identifying those relevant to components under their responsibility.
- For each relevant requirement, they defined corresponding system requirements. These were linked to the corresponding user requirement ID and prioritized accordingly.
- Each system requirement is mapped to a specific component within the platform to ensure traceability.
- The requirements have been structured in a table format consistent with the structure used in deliverable D2.1. [1]

To ensure completeness, system requirements were also extracted from features already implemented in the second version of the platform (as outlined in Table 1.) These requirements have been assigned a "Must" priority.

The new iteration of the system requirements is summarized in the table below.

System Requirement ID	User Requirement IDs	System Requirement Description	MoSCoW	Relevant component
Identity Management				
SYS_ID_1	2.1.10	The platform should be able to retrieve the list of registered users	Should	Identity Management
Content Management				
SYS_CM_1	2.1.10	The platform should provide the possibility to select contributors from a predefined list	Should	Content Management
SYS_CM_2	2.1.10	The platform should be able to filter the list of users by email	Should	Content Management
SYS_CM_3	1.1.3	The platform must support the creation of an NFT directly from an asset in the content management system.	Must	Content Management
SYS_CM_4	1.1.7	The platform must support tooltips in the UI that provide explanations on fields and/or processes.	Must	Content Management
SYS_CM_5	1.1.8, 2.1.4	The platform must enhance the UI and provide new capabilities in the content management system.	Must	Content Management
SYS_CM_6	2.1.5	The platform must enable the uploading of content directly within organisations and teams.	Must	Content Management

NFTs				
SYS_NFT_1	1.1.4	The platform must support work repositories as a content type.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_2	1.1.10	The platform should support a mechanism to manage the versions of assets.	Should	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_3	1.1.14	The platform should implement a derived version of the Token Bound License for NFTs.	Should	NFT Tool
SYS_NFT_4	1.1.12	The platform must support multiple versions of NFT instances for an asset.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_5	1.2.6	The platform could support the distribution of free items featuring a donate/support mechanism.	Could	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_6	2.1.8	The platform must support public access to the marketplace with capabilities limited to viewing.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_7	1.1.5	The platform must support additional information on the metadata of work repository NFTs, including work title, composer name and work version, for work repositories. Links to work author and work presentation.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_8	1.1.6	The platform must enable Markdown in assets' descriptions.	Must	Marketplace

SYS_NFT_9	1.1.13	The platform must implement a reputation system, that considers metrics and awards badges bases on marketplace items.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_10	2.1.6	The platform should feature an enhanced Marketplace design and layout, based on mock-ups and style designs	Should	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_11	2.1.7	The platform should enhance the visualisation of digital assets in the marketplace.	Should	Marketplace
SYS_NFT_12	1.1.11	The platform should allow the user to create a new version of an asset keeping the same licensing as the original asset.	Should	Marketplace
Blockchain Realm				
SYS_BR_1	1.2.3	The platform must be able to create and update Smart Contract for DAO Competition	Must	DAO System
Competition				
SYS_COM_1	1.2.3	The platform must be able to provide a list of closed competition	Must	Competition Tool

SYS_COM_2	1.2.3	The platform must be able to provide all the applications of a specific closed competition	Must	Competition Tool
DAOs				
SYS_DAO_1	1.2.3	The platform must be able to retrieve the closed competition	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_2	1.2.3	The platform must be able to retrieve the detail of a closed competition	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_3	1.2.3	The platform must be able to retrieve all the applications of a specific competition	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_4	1.2.3	The platform must provide to select options from the applications during the proposal creation	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_5	1.2.3	The platform must be able to manage hypertext (font, URL, images, etc.) for DAO proposal description	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_6	1.2.3	The platform must provide the possibility to vote to any user of the platform even if he/she registered after the creation of the proposal	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_7	1.2.3	The platform must provide the possibility to vote multiple options	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_8	1.2.4	The platform should provide the possibility to link a discord channel to a proposal	Should	DAO System

SYS_DAO_9	1.2.4	The platform should provide the possibility to generate a new thread in the DAFNE+ Discord DAO Channel and link it to the proposal	Should	DAO System
SYS_DAO_10	1.2.5	The platform should provide the possibility view DAFNE+ Common wallet (Treasure) to the Community	Could	DAO System
SYS_DAO_11	1.2.5	The platform should provide the possibility to increase/decrease the treasure wallet based on the proposal decisions	Could	DAO System
SYS_DAO_12	1.2.1	The platform must provide a DAO that enables the managing of a single community.	Must	DAO System
SYS_DAO_13	1.2.2	The platform must enable DAO capabilities for creating a new proposal, voting on proposals and discussing proposal.	Must	DAO System
UI				
SYS_UI_1	2.1.2	The platform must provide in the landing page content that represent the DAFNE+ value proposition	Must	DAFNE+ Platform
SYS_UI_2	2.1.9	The platform must provide a link to the DAFNE+ Discord Channel	Must	DAFNE+ Platform
SYS_UI_3	2.1.9	The platform must provide additional and updated documentation on	Must	DAFNE+ Platform

MetaMask, wallet configuration and token retrieving				
SYS_UI_4	2.1.1	The platform must provide consistent interfaces across all sections, ensuring uniformity in design and functionality.	Must	DAFNE+ platform
SYS_UI_5	2.1.3	The platform must redesign the connection to MetaMask button using its logo.	Must	DAFNE+ platform
FAQ and Chat				
SYS_FQ_1	2.2.1	The platform must provide sections in the FAQ, providing information on the acquisition and connection to a MetaMask wallet, acquisition of free tokens, creation of contents, minting, buying and selling of NFTs	Must	FAQ
Integration				
SYS_INT_1	1.1.1	The platform must support a stable connection to the MetaMask browser plugin.	Must	DAFNE+ Platform
SYS_INT_2	1.1.2	The platform must support the bidirectional connection of the NFT marketplace and the content management.	Must	Marketplace
SYS_INT_3	1.3.1	The platform must integrate with Matomo to provide insights on the activity of users in specific events.	Must	DAFNE+ Platform

5 DAFNE+ high level architecture

5.1 Introduction

Starting from the user and system requirements, together with the technical specifications of the architectural components, the first version of the DAFNE+ architecture was released in June 2023. The DAFNE+ Architecture aimed to represent the DAFNE+ platform and toolset both from a visual and technical perspective, describing all the technical layer as well as the components that are part of the overall platform. The Figure 1 below shows the first version of the DAFNE+ Architecture as reported in D2.1 [1]

FIGURE 1: FIRST VERSION OF THE DAFNE+ ARCHITECTURE

Following this first version DAFNE+ Architecture, the DAFNE+ Platform was implemented as a multi-layer platform in which many components collaborate with each other for implementing an overall ecosystem in which the end-user is able to collaborate and share content, defining innovative business models and revenue mechanisms.

The first version of integrated platform, delivered in November 2023 implemented part of the components described in the architecture:

- Content Manager
- NFT Marketplace
- Tools Catalogue and Tools UI (exclude the Automatic Art Generator)
- FAQ and Chat
- Identity and Profile Management
- Blockchain Realm
- Integration Layer
- Storage Layer

In addition to this, the remaining components was implemented, integrated and released in the intermediate version released in October 2024. This version also included:

- DAO system
- AI Recommender

Additional information about features of the platform in the two released versions, can be found in D4.2 [4] and D4.3 [5]. Downstream of DAFNE+ Platform releases, several validations with end-users were conducted in order to evaluate the overall DAFNE+ Platform ecosystem, including the components, the UI and UX. This validation phase allowed to the user and technical partners to revise some processes and requirements of the overall platform, including the possibility to implements new requirements as described in chapter 3 and 4.

These updates and new requirements impacted in the conceptual view of the DAFNE+ Architecture, which was revised in order to cover all the new features to be implemented for the final release of the DANFE+ Platform.

5.2 Architecture Updates

The outcome of the collaborative work presented in chapter 3.3 has shaped the description of the system requirements presented in chapter 4. Subsequently, the description of the new features agreed among the use case and technical partners to be included in the final version are detailed here.

In terms of components, the most relevant change is related to the **Version Management**, now fully integrated in the Marketplace tool as dedicated features for versioning the creation and re-usage of NFTs. Accordingly, to this aspect, also the LFS system storage was removed since no more necessary for the versioning feature. In addition, based on specific request of user partners a new tool was implemented and fully integrated with the DAO system: the **Competition tool**. Finally, a small change was related to the AI Recommender tool that is now used directly by the marketplace to suggest NFTs based on user profiling. The Figure 2 below shows the updated version of the DAFNE+ Architecture.

FIGURE 2: FINAL VERSION OF THE DAFNE+ ARCHITECTURE

5.2.1 DAO For Competition

The DAO system implemented and integrated in the intermediate version of the DAFNE+ Platform was initially designed for managing the DAFNE+ Community, implementing rules and governance models based on smart contracts and blockchain.

The rules ensure that all members of the DAFNE+ Community have a fair and known representation and decision-making power as well as an equitable distribution of resources and the revenues generated by the platform.

The main goal of the DAFNE+ Community DAO is to be collectively owned and governed by the users that can become owners and decision-makers of the platform and derive part of their livelihood from it.

The DAO system consists of:

- DAO Participation mechanisms, a unique NFT is generated and assigned to each member of the DAFNE+ Community.
- Proposal creation, any participant is able to create configurable proposal that can include several information such as: title, description, timeline (for vote), quorum (required for votes to be considered), threshold (minimum number of votes a Proposal must obtain in order to be accepted).
- Voting, any participant is able to vote other participants proposal in a secure and transparent way.

In this second phase of the project the DAO system will be extended and integrated with an additional tool: the DAO for Competition.

DAO for Competition can be intended as a tool that leverages on the technical characteristics of the DAO (based on blockchain and smart contracts) for creating fair and transparent competitions where the creatives can participate publishing their own digital asset.

The Competition tool exploits the already existing mechanisms for DAO Proposal and voting and it is integrated with the Content Manager for the digital asset publication (applications). The Competition consists of two different stages:

- Competition creation and Application
- Proposal creation and Voting

The first stage includes two main actors: the administrator, which has the role to create and manage competitions and the participant, which is a classical end-user of the DAFNE+ Platform able to create assets and link them to a specific competition.

The administrator can:

- Manage (create and edit) multiple competitions.
- Configure a competition with several details (type of asset, enriched description, timeline).

The participant can:

- Navigate the competition section.
- View list and details of all the ongoing competitions.
- Create new asset and link to a specific competition.
- Link existing asset to a specific competition.
- Unlink linked asset from a specific competition.

The second stage is strictly related to the concept of DAO, in which a community can participate in a decision in a fair and transparent way. In this case, the voting system implemented for DAO system will be also used for implementing the Competition voting system.

The new section of DAO (DAO for Competition) will be only available for the Administrator role. In fact, after the end of the first stage (end of applications) each Competition must be voted by the DAFNE+ Community and a DAO Competition proposal must be created for that.

A DAO Competition proposal is linked to a unique Competition and will include additional features compared to the first version of DAO proposal. Among these:

- Proposal auto full filled with Competition info (title, description, etc.)
- Options automatically pre-selected from all the applications. Options can be selected or unselected also in a manual way
- Multiple-choice voting

- Everyone can vote (also users registered after proposal creation)

The complete list of requirements is provided in chapter 3.

Figure 3 below shows a use case diagram with Competition tool actors and functionalities.

FIGURE 3: USE CASE DIAGRAM WITH COMPETITION TOOL ACTORS AND FUNCTIONALITIES

The Competition tool will be used during the first evaluation phase from December 2024 to February 2025 for the RAVE Challenge, a competition organized by IRCAM. The goal of this challenge is to support the artists on AI models creation and to collectively establish a repertoire of RAVE models, allowing everyone to benefit from the richness and variety of approaches in the field of timbre/music transfer.

In order to fit the timing of the Rave Challenge, the definition of the requirements and the implementation of the Competition tool have already started.

The Competition Tool and all the features related to the first stage were already implemented and the tool is already available in the production environment of the DAFNE+ Platform.

5.2.2 Versioning system

A versioning system will be implemented in the last version of the platform. The feature will be integrated into the DAFNE+ marketplace to the tracking of derivatives and new enhancements of original content. The system is expected to foster aspects of collaboration in the marketplace and align with the community needs as reported in chapter 3.3.1.1.

Upon creating an item in the marketplace, users will have two different options regarding licensing:

- Non-Derivative (ND).
- Share-alike (SA).

If a creator opts for the ND license, then users will not be able to create new versions of the specific item, and the versioning capabilities will be disabled. When a creator selects the SA alike license the creator acknowledges that users will be able to create new versions of this asset.

For reasons of simplicity, alignment with the needs of use-cases, and as the legal implications of creating new versions of NFT items have not been thoroughly examined at the point of implementation, the consortium has decided that SA licensing will only apply to items distributed for free, and not NFTs. Therefore, choosing to create items with a SA license will direct user to the free item workflow.

Items that have the versioning enabled will display a button similar to fork, that will allow the users to create a new version of the item, specifying the version number as follows:

- New iterations: the numbering should be at the same level as the original, adding a sub-level in an incrementing manner.
- Derivatives: a new level should be defined in an incrementing manner.

A new item can be inherited only from one original asset, derivative or iteration, therefore specifying the utilising the versioning system should be simple, and intuitive for the users, following the principles of platforms they might already be familiar with, for example GitHub.

The versioning system will refine the marketplace item page and provide the ability to discover the derivatives/iterations of assets.

This feature will be reported in depth in deliverable D4.4 - Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration (final version), in M36.

5.2.3 Additional features for meeting new/modified requirements

Content Manager

The Content Manager is able to cover the complete media asset management value chain: creation, management and distribution of the content. The entire workflow has been integrated to the Blockchain Realm and specific smart contracts were implemented for: ensuring asset ownership, tracking data access management and for the definition of collaboration and relate remuneration. The Content Manager features were extensively tested during the evaluation and some interesting feedback was collected and reported in D2.3.

Main feedback was related to some difficulties on the usage of the platform and in particular to the connection of the MetaMask plugin and accessing the related blockchain features. Furthermore, the importance of having the Content Management and the NFT Marketplace strictly connected was also highlighted.

In order to address the collected feedback, the Content Manager was already extended implementing the following functionalities:

- the possibility to create NFT directly from the Content Management
- additional type of contents (e.g., Work repository)
- facilitation of the usage of the Content Management (video tutorial and tooltips)
- revisioning of the Organisation and Teams section (both in terms of UI and functionalities)

For the final version of the Content Manager, only some small updates are expected. In particular, the following requirement need to be covered:

- User in a drop-down menu to search for collaborators: In order to implement this, the Content Manager will offer the possibility to search collaborators within the users of the DAFNE+ Platform, both via email and/or wallet address.

Marketplace

The DAFNE+ Marketplace at its core is the place where the users are able to buy and sell assets under appropriate and transparent IPR licenses and revenue models. The assets supported are of any type of multimedia content like images, videos, audio files as well as work repositories.

The DAFNE+ Marketplace was probably the most tested section of the DAFNE+ Platform. In fact, minting and publish NFTs is the most interesting and impacting feature of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Following the feedback collected and reported in D2.3 [3] the following features were already implemented in the current version of the Marketplace:

- Possibility to create NFT based on work repository
- Better visualization of assets depending on the type (e.g., visualization of 3d models) and different use cases, including external link to author profile and work presentation
- Moderation system for administrator, in which users have the ability to report items violating the community rules of DAFNE+
- Items reputational system, based on user preferences and badges mechanisms
- Recommendation engine integration for providing a tailored experience to the DAFNE+ users
- Overall revision of UX/UI

In terms of architecture of the NFT Marketplace didn't have any big change. However, updates have been implemented through integrations with other DAFNE+ services to provide an enhanced experience to the users. marketplace with its subcomponent, the NFT Tool, and the integrated services is provided in the Figure 4 below.

FIGURE 4: ARCHITECTURE OF THE MARKETPLACE AND THE NFT TOOLS

Additional details on the new features implemented on the NFT Marketplace are reported in D4.3 [5].

The final version of the Marketplace should be further extended for implementing the additional requirements elicited and reported in chapter 4. Most of these requirements are in fact quite impactful for the Marketplace and a technical evaluation will allow to prioritize them for the final release. The following requirements should be considered to be implemented in the final release of the platform:

- **Public view of the marketplace:** To attract more users, and enhance the discoverability of the DAFNE+ marketplace, unauthenticated users that do not belong to the DAFNE+ ecosystem access the Marketplace with capabilities being restricted to only viewing the pages and content.
- **Implementing a versioning system:** as already described in the previous paragraph, the asset versioning system has been revised and a series of requirements have emerged to implement different versioning mechanisms within the marketplace. More details are reported in chapter 5.2.2

- Manage multiple NFT instances for an asset: the number of NFT instances may be predefined by the owner.

DAO

The community management and the implementation of the DAO system was part of the intermediate release.

As described in D4.3 [5] in the first implementation of the DAO, a single community will be managed: the DAFNE+ Governance DAO. This first DAO was used as a testing community for implementing basic functionalities for DAO Management that will allow the possibility to manage the DAFNE+ Platform governance (business models, implementation, etc.). Main features of the first version of DAFNE+ DAO system included:

- NFT Governance for DAFNE+ DAO: a SoulBound³ NFT token (non-transferrable) is assigned to each user as participant of the DAFNE+ community
- Create, discuss, and vote DAO proposals: any user has the possibility to create, discuss and vote DAO proposals in order to manage and evolve the DAFNE+ community

These features were implemented leveraging on the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm, exploiting the blockchain and smart contracts features for all the DAO mechanisms, ensuring transparency and security among DAO community for the DAFNE+ governance aspects.

The first version of the DAFNE+ DAO system plan to be extended in the final stage of the project for supporting additional features or communities such as the implementation of DAO for Competition as described in chapter 5.2.1

In addition, the following requirements should be addressed in the final implementation of DAO system, following the requirements elicited and reported in chapter 3:

- DAO discussion space - Discord link: Discord channels are important communication and social environments for DAO communities. In the first version of the DAO system the proposal creator has

³ <https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-5484>

the possibility to link an existing Discord channel to the proposal. Based on the feedback of the end-users, the proposal should be adapted giving the possibility to automatically create a discord thread for each proposal in the DANFE+ DAO Discord channel

- DAFNE+ treasury flow: the DAFNE+ platform already have a common wallet (Treasury) that allow to execute any smart contracts feature. In the final version the DAFNE+ Platform should be able to create fund allocation directly from the DAO proposal. A minimum requirement can be the visualization of the common wallet in the UI of the DAFNE+ DAO section in order to visualize how much the common wallet is gaining from the platform fees.

Landing Page and Documentation

Following the feedback during the first validation phase, was clear the necessity to have more information about the characteristics and features offered by DFANE+ platform for the new users.

The main issues during the validation process with end-users were mainly related to the connection of MetaMask wallet and more in general on the execution of the blockchain-based processes.

In order to support the users during the onboarding process, the DAFNE+ Platform FAQ section was extended for including additional technical documentation and video tutorials that can facilitate the accessibility to the main functionalities, including among others: MetaMask Wallet connection, creation of contents, minting, buying and selling of NFT. These video tutorials were also published in the official DAFNE+ YouTube channels and linked in the main page of the DAFNE+ Platform after the login process.

For the final version of the platform is first of all crucial to **keep update all the documentation for supporting the updated and/or new features** implemented within the DAFNE+ Platform.

In addition, is important to consider the following updates:

- **Platform landing page with value proposition:** the DAFNE+ Platform landing page (before login/registration) should explain the benefits of the platform (What, Why & How), what the users can do with it. The video can be also moved in the entry page.

- **Link to Discord:** it is important to have a direct and visible link to discord channel for users to connect (outside of the platform) a participate in DAFNE+ community discussions.
- **Documentation on acquisition of new tokens:** as already mentioned is important to keep updated the overall platform documentation and in particular to prepare a new video tutorial for MetaMask installation, focusing on the configuration of the new Polygon network (Amoy) and the acquisition of the new Polygon Token (POL).

6 Conclusion

The revised user requirements presented in this document stemming from the work that is conducted both in the framework of the use cases and the outcomes of the pilots, but also through platform testing activities and constructive discussions realized in the framework of the project. This, led to the formulation of the updated system requirements which subsequently were reflected into the design of the final version of the DAFNE+ platform architecture that is described in the deliverable. The materialization of the collaborative work that was conducted during the project duration and the strong user-centric approach that the project has adopted establishes the foundation upon which the final version of the DAFNE+ platform will be developed by the technical work packages and which will be offered to the DAFNE+ users. At the same time, apart from the functional enhancements that were specified here, special effort was put on delivering significantly improved user experience to the end-user.

7 References

- [1] DAFNE+, “D2.1 - User requirements and DAFNE+ architecture,” 2024.
- [2] DAFNE+, “D2.2 - DAFNE+ use case specifications,” 2023.
- [3] DAFNE+, “D2.3 - DAFNE+ use case specifications (final report),” 2024.
- [4] DAFNE+, “D4.2 - Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration,” 2023.
- [5] DAFNE+, “D4.3 - Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report),” 2024.

